

ISic3433

Epitaph for Belleia Vesonio

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2017.07.20 (Prag)

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

Found within a funerary building within the area designated 'recinto B' by Paolo Orsi during excavation in 1914 of the

Coordinates

38.1992517, 15.5566385

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Museo regionale
interdisciplinare di Messina, inventory A3554

Physical Description

A rectangular tablet of white marble with dark veining; slight chipping to the edges.

Dimensions

Height 19.5 cm

Width 35 cm

Depth 1.5 cm

Layout

Latin text laid out neatly over four lines, neatly filling the available space (regular left margin, irregular right margin). Line 1 has large hedera at each end.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Neatly v-cut letters, with faint traces of guidelines. The letters have deep serifs at the end of strokes: E is often very narrow, with the horizontal bars angled upwards; M and A in the final line have extended upper strokes, tending towards cursive; interpuncts are variable in form.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 27 mm

Lines 2-4: 30 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation lines 1 to 4: 8-11 mm

Text

1. D(is) · M(anibus) ·
2. BelleiaVelleia · Vesonia · vix(it) ·
3. ann(is) · XXXIII · L(ucius) · Ostrius ·
4. Crescens · uxori · rarissimae ·

Apparatus

Text based upon Bitto 2001 and controlled against photograph

Translation (en)

To the shades of the underworld. Belleia Vesonia lived for 34 years. Lucius Ostrius Crescens for his extraordinary wife.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284771

EDR 033611

EDCS 14805792

PHI 313624

Bibliography

Bitto, I. 2001. Le iscrizioni greche e latine di Messina. *Pelorias* 7. Messina. At 1

Orsi, P. 1916. Messana. La necropoli romana di S. Placido e di altre scoperte avvenute nel 1910-1915. *Monumenti Antichi*. 24: 121-218. At 133 fig.8

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